

Opportunities for exploitation of Earth Observation data to inform risk management of ocean tipping points

Richard Wood, Alessandra Conversi, Reik Donner, Angela Landolfi, Anastasia Romanou, Thomas Stocker, Didier Swingedouw, Wieslaw Maslowski

This note summarises ideas for the exploitation of EO data to move forward the science of ocean tipping points, with the goal of enabling societies to better manage the risks associated with such events. It is the result of discussions among the authors at the ISSI Workshop on understanding EO needs for tipping points, held in Bern in October 2022.

1. Current Understanding and Observation of Ocean Tipping Points

The ocean contains a number of potential tipping elements, for which there is theoretical, observational or palaeoclimatic evidence that abrupt changes are possible when climatic forcing passes some threshold. The following summarizes some key ocean tipping elements within two broad categories: (a) ocean circulation and sea ice, and (b) ocean ecosystems and biogeochemical cycles.

a. Ocean circulation:

- i. Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). There is extensive evidence from Earth System Models, theoretical models and palaeoclimate analyses that the AMOC has the potential for major regime shifts or collapse, which would have major, widespread impacts on global climate. While there is broad consensus that such an event is unlikely in the 21st Century, substantial uncertainty remains due to deficiencies in current climate model representation of the AMOC. In recent years *in situ* AMOC monitoring arrays have been put in place at different latitudes (RAPID, OSNAP, SAMBA), while some studies show promise for AMOC monitoring through indirect methods such as inversion of satellite data and data assimilation into models.
- ii. Atlantic Sub-polar Gyre (SPG). A collapse of convection in the sub-polar gyre would be a smaller-scale event compared to a complete AMOC collapse but it would still have substantial impacts on climate around the North Atlantic, and could be a critical step on a path to AMOC collapse. It could occur more quickly than AMOC collapse (years rather than decades) and could be considered more likely as it is seen in many climate model experiments. Current EO observations such as altimetry, and *in situ* observations such as Argo and repeat hydrographic sections, can sample changes in large scale gyre circulation and water masses, but do not currently provide information on individual convective events or their statistics.
- iii. Arctic Circulation and Sea Ice: Qualitative shifts in the Arctic climate system could arise through the emergence of seasonal or year-round ice-free conditions, their linkages with land hydrology, riverine fluxes, or a collapse of the Arctic halocline, as well as interactions with lower latitude oceans. Such changes in the Arctic climate system will expose deeper ocean layers to atmospheric heat exchange, with impacts on regional ecosystems and greenhouse gas release/storage, as well as on glacial/ice sheet melt, and the stability of AMOC and SPG through freshwater export. Uncertainty in modelling such climatic shifts arises not only from model spatio-temporal resolution, but also from limited observations of key processes and feedbacks involving the Arctic sea ice and upper ocean (e.g., sea ice and snow thickness distribution, sea surface temperature/salinity, upper ocean mixed layer depth and stratification). This uncertainty extends to critical impacts on the exchanges through the main Arctic Ocean gateways (Canadian Archipelago, Bering, Davis, and Fram straits), the Subarctic boundary currents, and deep-water formation.
- iv. Western Boundary Currents (WBC). In the North Pacific, the Kuroshio Current is known to switch spontaneously between two paths, with states persisting for several

years and transitions occurring over a few months. Similar, if less pronounced transitions are seen in the Gulf Stream. The impacts of such shifts are probably less widespread than for the AMOC and SPG.

- v. Marine heat waves. Increased frequency, intensity and duration of positive persistent anomalies in the sea surface temperature are already observed in the last two decades, and studies suggest that they might have recently crossed a tipping point to a less synchronised space-time structure. There is however large uncertainty about how these features will evolve under future warming scenarios.

b. *Ocean ecosystems and biogeochemical cycles:*

- i. *Biogeochemical cycles.* Current models show large uncertainty around the intensity and timescales of the forcing required to trigger abrupt biogeochemical changes such as a wide extension of ocean deoxygenation and acidification, or abrupt decline in productivity and biodiversity. The primary observational need at this stage is to better constrain biogeochemical processes in climate models in order to reduce modelling uncertainties in the thresholds and timescales of tipping or regime shifts. Particular variables of interest include chlorophyll-a, light absorption and backscattering, particulate organic carbon (POC), and more widespread availability of HYPER-spectral remote sensing reflectances. A further priority is developing methods to combine EO data with *in situ* data (e.g. BioArgo) to generate 3-dimensional reconstructions of key variables such as POC, O₂ and nutrients.
- ii. *Ocean ecosystems.* Near-surface planktonic ecosystems sustain the majority of the marine food web, which in turn supports billions of people worldwide. Because such ecosystems are highly mobile, the global coverage of EO is essential to monitor their behaviour. Observations (decadal time series) have shown that phyto- and zoo-plankton communities in most ocean basins have undergone abrupt shifts, and recent global models have indicated that the frequency and intensity of (zooplankton) shifts have increased in recent decades, with further increases projected. EO provides invaluable tools for understanding the potential for tipping in near-surface ecosystems on a global scale, and the time is right for combining remote observations with *in situ* time series and global models, to develop additional indicators for monitoring plankton and wider food chain productivity. Further needs include: using EO to detect tipping points in ecosystem features that impact on dimethyl sulphide (DMS) emissions (to better understand ocean-atmosphere feedbacks); and monitoring marine heat waves and acidification as potential drivers of tipping of both near-surface and sea-floor ecosystems.

For many of the above tipping elements, as well as monitoring there is a strong driver to develop observable *early warning indicators* of approaching tipping points, providing time to prepare, build resilience, and adapt to upcoming major shifts.

2. Opportunities for Exploitation of EO data

The main opportunities identified are centred around the theme of consistently combining multiple observations (EO and *in situ*) to address current knowledge gaps in ocean and sea ice tipping points. There are three main applications:

- a. Combine multiple observed variables, from EO and *in situ* sources, and models, to deliver a step change in the ability to **monitor and detect changes in key ocean tipping elements** (e.g. major changes in the AMOC/subpolar gyre or Arctic sea ice; the statistics of marine heat waves or acidification events; primary productivity; biogeochemical cycles). The scope may also include key **small-scale processes important for ocean tipping** that are not directly observed (e.g. boundary currents, transports through complex regions such as the Canadian Archipelago and critical

ocean straits, and convection in the subpolar North Atlantic). Advances may be delivered through empirical methods (e.g. fingerprinting, emulation, machine learning) or through targeted assimilation into physical models.

- b. Use climate models showing tipping points in the ocean to identify spatial-temporal patterns of remotely sensed and *in situ* observed variables, that would provide **early warning of approaching tipping**¹. The early warning might be provided through empirical analysis methods (e.g machine learning, dynamical systems analysis), or through targeted improvements to the initialisation/calibration of decadal predictions. An important output of this work would be to define the *precision, accuracy* and *timescale* of observations required to deliver practical warning systems.
- c. Exploit EO and in situ datasets for **targeted model evaluation, driving improvement of key processes relevant to ocean tipping in next generation Earth System models**. Potential model developments include resolving key small-scale processes, and improved/better constrained parametrisations of relevant physical, biogeochemical and ecosystem processes.

¹ See Swingedouw et al. 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-020-09604-6> for a recent, more detailed discussion of some potential uses of EO in this area.